

Protection of stainless steels by Mo against Cl-attack: a DFT study

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S1: Methods

Surface models

Both chromia ($\alpha\text{-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$) and hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), hereafter denoted as Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 , respectively, have the corundum structure in which the O atoms form a hexagonal close-packed lattice with $2/3$ of the O octahedral sites occupied by Cr or Fe atoms. The (0001) surfaces of chromia and hematite are of interest here since the inner layers of the oxide films formed on body-centred cubic Cr(110) [1] and FeCr(110) [2a], and on face-centred cubic FeCrNi(100) [2b]) are oriented along the [0001] direction.

As concluded in our previous studies [3-4], (0001)-oriented Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 surfaces in aqueous environment have double-M (M refers to Cr or Fe) terminations with high degree of hydroxylation ($-\text{Cr}_2\text{-(OH)}_3$ and $-\text{Fe}_2\text{-(OH)}_{2\sim 3}$). Thus, only double-M

terminations will be considered in this study.

Symmetric slab configuration was used, containing a frozen bulk-like cell in the centre and identical surface cells on each side of the slab. The details to obtain hydroxylated surface cells are described in our previous work [4]. **Figure S1** shows the symmetric slab with fully hydroxylated Cr_2O_3 surface cells as an example. The operations to substitute atoms or to create vacancies were carried out systematically on each side of slabs to keep the symmetry. The fully hydroxylated surface cells ($-\text{O}_3-\text{M}_2-(\text{OH})_3$) contain 3 OH per 1×1 unit cell, corresponding to a surface concentration of 10^{19} m^{-2} . The ratio between the surface hydroxyl groups and the terminating metal atoms that bear the hydroxyl groups is 1.5 with each OH bridging two metal atoms.

Figure S1. Symmetric slab of fully hydroxylated (0001)-oriented Cr_2O_3 surfaces.

Substitution of OH by Cl was simulated by replacing the neutral hydroxyl groups by the same number of neutral Cl atoms, i.e., keeping the same ratio between the terminating metal atoms and their bearing groups (Cl or OH). This operation is equivalent to substituting OH^- by Cl^- if the hydroxyl groups and Cl atoms adsorbed on hydroxylated surfaces are in the oxidation state of -1, which will be further verified

using Bader charge analysis.

We adopt the nomenclature (p Cl + q OH), where p and q are the numbers of Cl and OH per unit cell, respectively. The surface with highest Cl coverage (3 Cl + 0 OH) corresponds to three Cl per unit cell. The lowest Cl coverage studied in the present work corresponds to one single Cl per 2×2 supercell (with eleven OH groups if fully covered). In this case, we note the surface cell as (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH).

Before surface relaxation, Cl on the surface was initially set at the bulk position of O in Cr_2O_3 (or Fe_2O_3), as for O of the added OH groups [4]. On the hydroxylated surface cells (0 Cl + 2 OH) and (0 Cl + 3 OH), the OH groups to be substituted to obtain the surface cells (1 Cl + 1 OH), (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH), (1 Cl + 2 OH) and (2 Cl + 1 OH) are equivalent, i.e., substituting different OH groups by Cl yields the same surface structure and energy. This was verified with the surface cell (2 Cl + 1 OH).

On surfaces with and without Cl, the investigated defects include substitutional Mo and cationic and anionic vacancies. To study a high defect concentration (1 per surface unit cell), we simulated one defect in a 1×1 unit cell or four defects in a 2×2 supercell with each defect at the same site in the subcell. For low defect concentration (0.25 per unit surface cell), we simulated one defect in a 2×2 supercell.

Energetic

To study the free energy of substitution of p OH by Cl using symmetric slabs without

(“slab”) and with Cl (“slab·2pCl”), we considered the following reaction in which Cl⁻ coming from the electrolyte replaces OH⁻ released in the electrolyte and becoming H₂O immediately:

$$G_{\text{sub,Cl}} = \frac{1}{2p} (G_{\text{slab} \cdot 2p\text{Cl}} - G_{\text{slab}}) + \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l})}^0 - \mu_{\text{H}^+(\text{aq})}^0 + k_{\text{B}}T \ln(10) \text{pH} \\ - \mu_{\text{Cl}^-(\text{aq})}^0 - k_{\text{B}}T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{Cl}^-}}{c^0}\right) \quad (\text{I})$$

where G_{sub} is the free energy of substitution, G the free energy, μ^0 the standard chemical potential, k_{B} the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, c the concentration, and c^0 the standard concentration of 1 M. The chemical potential of liquid water $\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l})}^0$ was estimated from that of water vapor $\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})}^0$ and the evaporation free energy $\Delta G_{\text{evap,H}_2\text{O}}^0$. The estimations of the standard chemical potentials of H⁺ and Cl⁻ are described in the next section.

To be able to compute easily by DFT, we neglected the contributions from zero-point energy and vibrational entropy, which are often considered negligible for formation reaction. The same principle was also applied for the following formulation. The final expression for DFT-computable substitution (free) energy E_{sub} is then:

$$E_{\text{sub}} = \frac{1}{2p} (E_{\text{slab}\cdot 2p\text{Cl}} - E_{\text{slab}}) + E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})} - E_{\text{HCl}(\text{g})} - \Delta G_{\text{evap},\text{H}_2\text{O}}^0 - \Delta G_{\text{diss},\text{HCl}}^0 \quad (2)$$

$$- \Delta G_{\text{sol},\text{HCl}}^0 + k_{\text{B}}T \ln(10) \text{pH} - k_{\text{B}}T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{Cl}^-}}{c^0}\right)$$

where E is the energy computed by DFT, and $\Delta G_{\text{sol},\text{HCl}}^0$ and $\Delta G_{\text{diss},\text{HCl}}^0$ the standard free energies of solution and dissociation of HCl, respectively.

To study the direct addition of one Cl on slabs with not fully covered surfaces (“slab $\cdot 2(p-1)\text{Cl}$ ”) to form slabs with fully covered surfaces (“slab $\cdot 2p\text{Cl}$ ”), we considered the (free) energy of direct addition

$$E_{\text{add,Cl}} = \frac{1}{2} (E_{\text{slab}\cdot 2p\text{Cl}} - E_{\text{slab}\cdot 2(p-1)\text{Cl}}) - E_{\text{Cl,SHE}} \quad (3)$$

where

$$E_{\text{Cl,SHE}} = E_{\text{HCl}(\text{g})} - \frac{1}{2} E_{\text{H}_2(\text{g})} + \Delta G_{\text{diss},\text{HCl}}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{sol},\text{HCl}}^0 + k_{\text{B}}T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{Cl}^-}}{c^0}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$+ eU_{\text{SHE}}.$$

To study the substitution of s metal cations M by Mo using symmetric slabs without (“slab $\cdot 2\text{M}$ ”) and with (“slab $\cdot 2\text{Mo}$ ”) substitutional Mo, the (free) energy of substitution $E_{\text{sub,Mo}}$ was calculated using the following expression:

$$E_{\text{sub,Mo}} = \frac{1}{2} (E_{\text{slab}\cdot 2\text{Mo}} - E_{\text{slab}\cdot 2\text{M}}) + E_{\text{M}(\text{s})} - E_{\text{Mo}(\text{s})}. \quad (5)$$

Here the energies of the exchanged metal atoms M and Mo are those in the bulk metals since we considered the substitution at the alloy/oxide interface.

For the dissolution of oxide in the electrolyte due to vacancy formation, we used the energies of symmetric slabs without (“slab·2A”) and with (“slab·2Vac”) vacancies A (A for metal atom M or oxygen). The (free) energy of vacancy formation $E_{\text{vac},A}$ is then:

$$E_{\text{vac},A} = \frac{1}{2}(E_{\text{slab}\cdot 2\text{Vac}} - E_{\text{slab}\cdot 2A}) + E_{A,\text{SHE}} \quad (6)$$

where $E_{A,\text{SHE}}$ is the energy of atom A in the electrolyte expressed by:

$$E_{M,\text{SHE}} = E_{M(\text{s})} + k_{\text{B}}T \ln\left(\frac{c_{M^{q+}(\text{aq})}}{c^0}\right) + qeE_{M^{q+}/M}^0 - qeU_{\text{SHE}} \quad (7)$$

$$E_{\text{O},\text{SHE}} = E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})} - E_{\text{H}_2(\text{g})} - \Delta G_{\text{evap},\text{H}_2\text{O}}^0 + 2k_{\text{B}}T \ln(10) \text{pH} + 2eU_{\text{SHE}}. \quad (8)$$

For the following analyses, the temperature is chosen at 25 °C, the pH value at 1 and the applied potential at 0 V/SHE. As indicated by Equation (4) and Equation (8), the dependency on applied potential of the energies of Cl direct addition and the formation energies of O vacancies is the same in Cr_2O_3 as in Fe_2O_3 . The conclusion for these defects, obtained by comparing the results of Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 , is then independent of the choice of applied potential. For cationic defects, we consider that Cr and Fe dissolved in solutions have the oxidation states of +3 and +2, respectively. The difference between the formation energies of Cr and Fe vacancies is then linearly proportional to the applied potential, and here we set the potential at 0 V/SHE to make an example. By default, we consider that the concentrations of Cl⁻ and M^{q+} (Cr^{3+} or Fe^{2+}) in solutions are 10^{-3} and 10^{-6} M, respectively.

Atomic chemical potentials

To elaborate the energetic aspects of Cl adsorption, Mo substitution and vacancy formation of interest in this work, it is necessary to determine the atomic chemical potentials. Here we applied the CHE approach [5,6] to calculate the atomic chemical potentials in an electrochemical process. As explained in our previous work [4], the chemical potentials of H ($\mu_{\text{H,SHE}}$) and O ($\mu_{\text{O,SHE}}$) using a standard hydrogen electrode (SHE) as reference electrode can be written as:

$$\mu_{\text{H,SHE}} = \frac{1}{2}\mu_{\text{H}_2(\text{g})}^0 - k_{\text{B}}T \ln(10) \text{pH} - eU_{\text{SHE}} \quad (9)$$

$$\mu_{\text{O,SHE}} = \frac{1}{2}\mu_{\text{O}_2(\text{g})}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{f,H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})}^0 - \Delta G_{\text{evap,H}_2\text{O}}^0 + 2k_{\text{B}}T \ln(10) \text{pH} + 2eU_{\text{SHE}} \quad (10)$$

where μ^0 is the standard chemical potential, k_{B} the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, e the elemental charge, U_{SHE} the applied potential referenced to the SHE electrode, ΔG_{f}^0 the standard free energy of formation, and $\Delta G_{\text{evap,H}_2\text{O}}^0$ the standard free energy of evaporation of water obtained in the NIST chemistry webbook [7].

To avoid the electrolysis of water, the chemical potentials of O and H in the electrolyte should be lower than that in the gases. The limit of applied potential can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} -k_{\text{B}}T \ln(10) \text{pH} &< eU_{\text{SHE}} \\ &< -\frac{1}{2}\Delta G_{\text{f,H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})}^0 + \frac{1}{2}\Delta G_{\text{evap,H}_2\text{O}}^0 - k_{\text{B}}T \ln(10) \text{pH}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The same approach was used to obtain the chemical potential of Cl by considering the

oxidation of Cl⁻:

The reaction free energy $\Delta G_{\text{II,SHE}}$ with respect to SHE can be written as

$$\Delta G_{\text{II,SHE}} = \frac{1}{2}\mu_{\text{Cl}_2(\text{g})} - \mu_{\text{Cl,SHE}} \quad (12)$$

$$\mu_{\text{Cl,SHE}} = \mu_{\text{Cl}^{-}(\text{aq})}^0 + k_{\text{B}}T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{Cl}^{-}}}{c^0}\right) + \mu_{\text{H}^{+}(\text{aq})}^0 - \frac{1}{2}\mu_{\text{H}_2(\text{g})}^0 + eU_{\text{SHE}} \quad (13)$$

where μ is the chemical potential, c the concentration, and c^0 the standard concentration of 1 M.

The standard chemical potentials of H⁺ and Cl⁻ ions were estimated by the formation, the solution of gas and the dissociation of HCl:

$$\begin{aligned} &\mu_{\text{H}^{+}(\text{aq})}^0 + \mu_{\text{Cl}^{-}(\text{aq})}^0 \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\mu_{\text{H}_2(\text{g})}^0 + \frac{1}{2}\mu_{\text{Cl}_2(\text{g})}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{f,HCl}(\text{g})}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{diss,HCl}}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{sol,HCl}}^0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the standard free energy of solution ($\Delta G_{\text{sol,HCl}}^0$) and dissociation ($\Delta G_{\text{diss,HCl}}^0$) of HCl can be obtained in the literature [8].

Finally, the chemical potential of Cl can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{\text{Cl,SHE}} &= \frac{1}{2}\mu_{\text{Cl}_2(\text{g})}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{f,HCl}(\text{g})}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{diss,HCl}}^0 + \Delta G_{\text{sol,HCl}}^0 + k_{\text{B}}T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{Cl}^{-}}}{c^0}\right) \\ &+ eU_{\text{SHE}}. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

To avoid H₂ (SHE cathode) and Cl₂ (anode) gas generation, we need:

$$\begin{aligned}
 -k_B T \ln(10) \text{ pH} &< eU_{\text{SHE}} \\
 &< -\Delta G_{\text{f,HCl(g)}}^0 - \Delta G_{\text{diss,HCl}}^0 - \Delta G_{\text{sol,HCl}}^0 - k_B T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{Cl}^-}}{c^0}\right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

For the chemical potentials of metal M (Cr or Fe) in the electrolyte, we considered the dissolution of metal and its free energy with respect to SHE:

$$\Delta G_{\text{III,SHE}} = \frac{1}{q} \mu_{\text{M,SHE}} - \frac{1}{q} \mu_{\text{M(s)}}^0 \tag{17}$$

$$\mu_{\text{M,SHE}} = \mu_{\text{M}^{q+}(\text{aq})}^0 + k_B T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{M}^{q+}}}{c^0}\right) - q\mu_{\text{H}^+(\text{aq})}^0 + \frac{q}{2}\mu_{\text{H}_2(\text{g})}^0 - qeU_{\text{SHE}} \tag{18}$$

where q the charge state of ion M in the electrolyte.

When the electrode is polarized with respect to the standard electrode potential, no reaction will occur in standard conditions:

$$0 = \Delta G_{\text{III,SHE}}^0 = \frac{1}{q} \mu_{\text{M}^{q+}(\text{aq})}^0 - \frac{1}{q} \mu_{\text{M(s)}}^0 - \mu_{\text{H}^+(\text{aq})}^0 + \frac{1}{2} \mu_{\text{H}_2(\text{g})}^0 - eE_{\text{M}^{q+}/\text{M}}^0. \tag{19}$$

where $E_{\text{M}^{q+}/\text{M}}^0$ is the standard electrode potential obtained in CRC Handbook [9].

Finally, the chemical potential of Cr or Fe can be expressed as

$$\mu_{\text{M,SHE}} = \mu_{\text{M(s)}}^0 + k_B T \ln\left(\frac{c_{\text{M}^{q+}(\text{aq})}}{c^0}\right) + qeE_{\text{M}^{q+}/\text{M}}^0 - qeU_{\text{SHE}}. \tag{20}$$

Calculation details

All considered models and optimized structures were built and visualized using the Modelview visualization software developed by B. Diawara [10].

Energies of slabs and references were calculated by density functional theory (DFT) and most of the calculation details were presented in our previous work [4]. For Cl atoms, the standard version of pseudopotential was chosen. For Cl₂ and HCl gases, the final magnetic moment of Cl was always zero even with an initial magnetic moment of $2 \mu_B$, thus no initial magnetic moment was distributed to Cl on oxide surfaces. Since symmetric slabs were used, the total magnetic moment of slabs was set to zero to accelerate the calculation.

Bader charge analysis [11] was performed to investigate the charge state of atoms. As shown previously [12], Cr (or Fe) in bulk Cr₂O₃ (or Fe₂O₃) has a ratio of 0.6 between Bader charges and formal charges. This ratio was used in the present work to convert Bader charges to formal charges.

S2: Substitution of OH by Cl

Figure S2 shows the charge distribution for a Cr₂O₃ surface with low Cl coverage (0.25

Cl + 2.75 OH). The Bader charges of surface Cr and O are +1.8 and -1.2 e , respectively, similar to those calculated in bulk [12]. The Bader charge of Cl is about -0.6 e , higher than those of the Cl atoms adsorbed on anhydrous surfaces (-0.3 ~ -0.4 e [13,14]). The converted formal charges of H, Cl and O are +1, -1 and -2 e , respectively. It is thus verified that substituting neutral hydroxyl groups by Cl atoms can simulate the substitution of hydroxyl ions by Cl ions.

Figure S2. Bader and formal charges for the (0001)-oriented Cr_2O_3 surface (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH). Each point represents an atomic layer whose nature is indicated by the background image according to the [0001] coordinate.

S3: Not fully hydroxylated surfaces

Figure S3 shows highly, but not-fully hydroxylated surfaces. On these surfaces, zigzag -O-H- networks are formed, as reported previously [4]. Such networks are broken by the presence of substitutional Cl^- ($1 \text{ Cl} + 1 \text{ OH}$) and ($2 \text{ Cl} + 0 \text{ OH}$). These surfaces have similar surface structures for Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 .

Figure S3. Structures of highly but not fully covered (0001)-oriented Cr_2O_3 surfaces with different Cl coverages.

Figure S4 shows the energies of direct addition of Cl (Equation (3)) on highly but not fully covered surfaces to form fully covered surfaces. To study Cl direct addition resulting in surfaces ($0.25 \text{ Cl} + 2.75 \text{ OH}$), the surfaces ($0 \text{ Cl} + 2.75 \text{ OH}$) were simulated by removing the adsorbed Cl on 2×2 optimized surfaces ($0.25 \text{ Cl} + 2.75 \text{ OH}$). The

structures are not shown since the removal of the adsorbed Cl did not significantly alter the surface structure. The surfaces (0 Cl + 2.75 OH) were also simulated by removing a hydroxyl group on 2×2 optimized surfaces (0 Cl + 3 OH). For Cr_2O_3 , both methods yielded the same surface structures while for Fe_2O_3 , the surface obtained by removing a hydroxyl group on the fully hydroxylated surface (0 Cl + 3 OH) has more regular -O-H- networks but higher energy. Thus, the later surface was not considered further.

The energies are exothermic for surfaces with low Cl coverage (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH) and (1 Cl + 2 OH), indicating that not fully hydroxylated surfaces can adsorb Cl^- by direct addition in Cl-containing environments. As a result, only the surfaces fully covered by OH and Cl will be discussed in the following.

Figure S4. Energies of direct addition of Cl on highly covered (0001)-oriented Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 surfaces with different Cl coverages.

S4: Mo effect on Cl adsorption

The M1dn position is the most stable position, except for the (1 Cl + 2 OH) surfaces with substitutional Mo at sites “Cr2up” on Cr₂O₃ and at sites “Fe1dn” and “Fe2up” on Fe₂O₃ surfaces. These altered surface structures are similar. The structures of Cr₂O₃ unaltered and altered surfaces with substitutional Mo at sites “Cr1dn” and “Cr2up”, respectively, are shown in **Figure S5**.

Figure S5. Structures of the Cr₂O₃ surfaces (1 Cl + 2 OH) with one substitutional Mo per surface unit at the sites “Cr1dn” and “Cr2up”.

Figure S6 shows the energies of cation substitution by Mo at different substitutional sites on Cr₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ surfaces. The most stable sites for the substitutional Mo are “Cr1dn” or “Fe1dn” except for the Cr₂O₃ surface with low Cl coverage (1 Cl + 2 OH). On this surface, the energy of substitution by Mo at sites “Cr2up” (-0.88 eV) is 0.06 eV

more exothermic than at sites “Cr1dn” (-0.82 eV). An additional test on the Cr_2O_3 surface with lower Cl coverage (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH) showed an inverse trend: the energy of substitution by Mo at sites “Cr1dn” (-0.79 eV) is more exothermic than at sites “Cr2up” (-0.61 eV). The change of the most stable sites for substitution on the Cr_2O_3 surface (1 Cl + 2 OH) may be related to the alteration of surface structure (Figure S1). On Fe_2O_3 surface (1 Cl + 2 OH), the surface structure alteration induced by the presence of substitutional Mo at sites “Fe1dn” and “Fe2up” lowers the energies of substitution in both cases, so that the most stable site remains “Fe1dn”.

Figure S6. Energies of substitution of a cation by Mo at different sites on (0001)-oriented (a) Cr_2O_3 and (b) Fe_2O_3 surfaces.

Since the substitutional Mo is slightly more stable (0.06 eV) at sites “M2up” only on the Cr_2O_3 surface (1 Cl + 2 OH), we consider only substitution at sites “M1dn” to simplify the analyses in the following.

The case of lower Mo concentration in which one substitutional Mo is added on each 2×2 surface supercells (i.e. 0.25 Mo per surface unit) was also investigated. Only the

surfaces with low Cl coverage (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH) were studied since this Cl-covered Fe_2O_3 surface is the only stable one. Substitutional Mo was considered at sites “M1dn”, the closest to the adsorbed Cl^- , since we are interested in the effect of Mo on Cl adsorption. The surfaces with and without substitutional Mo have similar structures, not shown here. Figure S7 shows the energies of substitution of OH^- by Cl^- in an acid solution ($\text{pH} = 1$) containing Cl^- (0.001 M) at room temperature (25 °C). There is no significant effect of Mo concentration on Cl adsorption.

Figure S7. Energies of substitution of OH^- by Cl^- on (0001)-oriented Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 surfaces (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH) as function of Mo concentration.

S5: Cationic vacancies

Figure S8 shows the formation energies of cationic vacancies at different sites. On fully covered surfaces without substitutional Cl (0 Cl + 3 OH), the most stable sites for

forming the cationic vacancies are “M2dn” for both Cr₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃. With a low Cl coverage (1 Cl + 2 OH), the most stable site becomes “Cr1up” on the Cr₂O₃ surface, while it remains “Fe2dn” on the Fe₂O₃ surface. With higher Cl coverages, (2 Cl + 1 OH) and (3 Cl + 0 OH), the most stable sites are “M1up” for both Cr₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃.

For each oxide, as the vacancy site is more distant from the surface, the formation energies on surfaces with different Cl coverages should converge to the same value corresponding to the vacancy formation energy in the bulk. As shown in Figure, this convergence was observed for most of the surfaces in the second subsurface cation layer (“M3up” and “M3dn”), in agreement with a theoretical study of corundum oxide interfaces claiming that the electron redistribution is very strongly localized in one or two atomic layers close to the interface [15]. However, Figure S8 also shows that the fully Cl-substituted surface (3 Cl + 0 OH) can influence the Fe vacancy formation deeper in the bulk, down to the sixth subsurface cation layer (“M7dn”) as shown in Figure S9. Since this surface coverage is not thermodynamically favoured, the following discussion is limited to the second subsurface layer (“M3dn”).

Figure S8. Formation energies of cationic vacancies at different sites on Mo-free

(0001)-oriented Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 surfaces.

Figure S9 shows the formation energies of cationic vacancies at different sites on Mo-free Fe_2O_3 surfaces. Complete substitution of OH by Cl on the Fe_2O_3 surface (3 Cl + 0 OH) influences the formation energy of Fe vacancy even at the sixth subsurface cation layer (“M7dn”).

Figure S9. (a) Cationic sites and (b) formation energies of cationic vacancies at these sites on Mo-free Fe_2O_3 surfaces.

An additional test was performed for the low Cl-covered Cr_2O_3 surface (1 Cl + 2 OH) with substitutional Mo at sites “Cr2up”. The formation energies on such surface are shown in Figure S10. In this case with substitutional Mo at sites “Cr2up”, the lowest formation energy is similar to that with substitutional Mo at sites “Cr1dn”, but the most stable site for vacancies becomes “Cr2dn” rather than “Cr1up”. This suggests that the presence of substitutional Mo favors the formation of cationic vacancies nearby (vacancies at “Cr2dn” for Mo at “Cr2up” and vacancies at “Cr1up” for Mo at “Cr1dn”) and erases the influence of surface adsorbates on the vacancy formation (vacancies at “M1up” or “M2dn” for surfaces without Mo and only at “M1up” for surfaces with Mo).

Figure S10. Formation energies of cationic vacancies at different sites on Cr_2O_3 surfaces (1 Cl + 2 OH) with substitutional Mo at the site “Cr2up”.

S6: Oxygen vacancies

Oxygen vacancies are equivalent on the surfaces (0 Cl + 3 OH) and (3 Cl + 0 OH), but not for the others. On surfaces (1 Cl + 2 OH) and (2 Cl + 1 OH), the oxygen vacancy formation was preliminarily tested at different sites to determine the most stable site for each atomic layer. Inequivalent sites for oxygen vacancy formation on the Cr_2O_3 surface (2 Cl + 1 OH) are shown as an example in Figure S11. The choice of vacancy formation site did not significantly influence the formation energies of vacancies in the “O2” and “O3” layers. The formation energies of vacancies at different sites of “O1” layers are shown in Table S2 and only the vacancies at the most stable sites were considered further. On surfaces (0.25 Cl + 2.75 OH), it was considered that the most stable site for each atomic layer is the same as on surfaces (1 Cl + 2 OH).

Figure S11. Inequivalent sites for oxygen vacancy formation on the Cr_2O_3 surface (2 Cl + 1 OH).

Figure S11 shows the inequivalent sites for oxygen vacancy formation on the Cr_2O_3 surface (2 Cl + 1 OH). These sites are equivalent on the surfaces (0 Cl + 3 OH) and (3 Cl + 0 OH), but not for the surfaces (1 Cl + 2 OH) and (2 Cl + 1 OH). Meanwhile, the choice of sites does not significantly influence the formation energies of vacancies at “O2” and “O3” layers. Table S1 shows the formation energies of oxygen vacancies at “O1” layer.

Table S1. Formation energies of oxygen vacancies at “O1” layers.

	Cr_2O_3			Fe_2O_3		
	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3
1 Cl + 2 OH (no Mo)	1.89	2.07	2.17	0.53	0.04	0.54
2 Cl + 1 OH (no Mo)	2.38	2.15	2.22	-0.22	-0.09	0.42
1 Cl + 2 OH (Mo at “Cr1dn”)	2.41	2.00	2.38	1.38	0.89	1.19
1 Cl + 2 OH (Mo at “Cr2up”)	2.20	2.12	2.33			
2 Cl + 1 OH (Mo at “Cr1dn”)	2.30	2.36	2.30	0.44	0.53	1.26

Figure S12 shows the formation energies of oxygen vacancies at different atomic layers.

Oxygen vacancies are the most stable at “O1” layer except for surfaces (0 Cl + 3 OH)

where the formation energies of oxygen vacancies at “O2” layer are nearly the same as those at “O1” layer, indicating that adsorbed Cl favors the formation of surface compared to subsurface oxygen vacancies. We observed a more marked effect of Cl on the O vacancy formation in Fe_2O_3 than in Cr_2O_3 , again suggesting that the Fe-rich zones of passive films are weak points for passivity.

Figure S12. Formation energies of oxygen vacancies at different sites on Mo-free (0001)-oriented (a) Cr_2O_3 and (b) Fe_2O_3 surfaces.

S7: Mo effect on oxygen vacancy formation

Figure S13 shows the formation energies of oxygen vacancies with Mo substituted at the “M1dn” sites. On Cr_2O_3 surfaces, the oxygen vacancy formation is not significantly influenced by the presence of Mo at the “M1dn” sites. The substitution by Mo at the “M2up” site was also tested on the Cr_2O_3 surface (1 Cl + 2 OH), which is not shown here, and no significant effect was observed either. On Fe_2O_3 surfaces, the formation energies of oxygen vacancies become 0.6 eV lower at the “O3” layer than at the “O1”

layer on the surface without Cl (0 Cl + 3 OH), while the most stable site of vacancies remains at the “O1” layers in the presence of Cl.

Figure S13. Formation energies of oxygen vacancies at different sites on Mo-substituted (0001)-oriented (a) Cr₂O₃ and (b) Fe₂O₃ surfaces.

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